

November 4, 2019

Search Committee
Department
University
Address
City, State, Zip

Dear Search Committee,

I am writing to apply for the position of Assistant Professor in <> at <institution>. Currently, I am a postdoctoral researcher and Moore data fellow at the University of Florida. As a computational ecologist, my work focuses on modeling population and community-level changes using data-driven methods. In addition, I am passionate about cultural and systemic change in academia to improve student training, inclusion, and accessibility. I am excited to apply and believe that I would be an excellent fit with the research and educational aims of this position.

Because ecosystems are incredibly complex, the observed patterns can arise from any number of underlying processes or their interactions. My research addresses this complexity using the data-centered framework of Empirical Dynamic Modeling (EDM) to filter for and capture the mechanisms that produced the observed changes. EDM relies on the mathematical principle that time series can themselves be sufficient for reconstructing the underlying dynamics. Although this approach is readily deployed for short-term forecasting, I am especially interested in developing methods that provide deeper understanding of ecological mechanisms using EDM. For example, in my paper on Fraser River sockeye salmon, I showed how to detect the influence of environmental factors on salmon recruitment, which was invisible to traditional fisheries models. Other examples of EDM applications include causal inference, reconstructing interaction networks, etc.

My current research builds on this foundation and expands the scope to include other forms of ecological change (abrupt shifts or critical transitions), increased scale (population time series from systems around the globe), and dataset complexity (spatially-structured or heterogeneous datasets). To meet the needs of each project, I assemble and lead collaborative teams, bringing in expertise on the system of study, software engineering, data management, statistical methods, and more. Because of my focus on tool and methods development, I recognize the importance of collaborating with other researchers who not only lend their expertise, but also identify novel research problems and applications. This approach has been beneficial to both my research productivity (21 peer-reviewed publications) and funding success (co-author on 5 funded proposals), and enhanced the impact of my work, spanning fields such as astrophysics, neuroscience, atmospheric sciences, and medicine.

These collaborations are facilitated by my open science practices: e.g. sharing datasets, code, open-access publications, etc. My philosophy is that science is cumulative and collaborative, and benefits from the diverse backgrounds and experiences of practitioners. By engaging in open science practices, I am able to lower the barrier for other researchers to build on my work and broaden participation in higher education, STEM, and academia. In addition to these practices, I embed the principles of inclusion and accessibility in my teaching and service work:

- I have training in evidence-based inclusive pedagogy, in the form of a 9-week course at UCSD as well as instructor training certification from The Carpentries.
- As an editor at *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, I strive to find reviewers across gender, geography, and career stage, using both the journal's database and the diversifyEEB list.
- Over the past two years, I have led the organization of Research Bazaar events in Gainesville, bringing together students, researchers, librarians, technologists, and more, to facilitate shared discussions around inclusive practices, data science, research, and careers.
- I am a co-leader of the Gainesville Ally Skills Network, promoting training in every practical action to address issues of inclusion and equity. In October, I co-taught a 3-hour workshop to staff, students, and postdocs at the University of Florida.

I would be delighted to bring my research, teaching, and diversity efforts to <institution>. In particular, I believe <specific details relevant to job fit> will be a great fit for this position.

As requested, enclosed with this application are my CV, research statement, teaching statement, diversity statement, and contact information for 3 references.

Thank you for your consideration, and I look forward to hearing from you.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, written over a horizontal line. The signature is stylized and appears to be the initials 'H. Z.' followed by a long, sweeping horizontal stroke that extends to the right.